

Urogenital tract and possible hormones affecting masculinization in female spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*)

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Abstract

The genital system of female spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) in the Hyaenidae family shows significant morphological and anatomical differences compared to other hyena species. The outer vagina found in other mammals is absent in spotted hyenas. The clitoris is enlarged, capable of erection, and has a penis-like appearance. This unique structure, called the pseudopenis or penile clitoris, has functional functions such as urination, mating, and childbirth. In the presented review, general information about female spotted hyenas is conveyed. In addition, studies on the possible effects of estrogen and androgens on the formation of the external genital tract are reviewed.

Keywords: Spotted hyena, sexual differentiation, penile clitoris, urogenital sinus, estrogens, androgens

1. INTRODUCTION

The largest members of the *Hyaenidae* family, spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) are one of the predatory wild mammal species living in Africa. Although spotted hyenas resemble dogs in appearance, they are more closely related to felines. Their closest living relatives are members of the *mongoose* and *civet* families, which are also carnivores. Although they are often thought to feed entirely on carrion, they are actually excellent hunters and primarily prey on large ungulates that they hunt themselves. An adult spotted hyena can meet its nutritional needs by hunting an antelope that is three times its own weight. Active during both the day and night, hyenas are capable of reproducing throughout the year. Hyenas play a vital role in African ecosystems, and their presence is an indicator of ecosystem health.¹

2. MORPHOLOGY IN SPOTTED HYENAS (*CROCUTA CROCUTA*)

Spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) are large carnivores, weighing between 40 and 80 kg. The background color of their fur is light grey, yellow, or red, with varying shades. On this background, there are dark spots in shades of black or brown. The spots fade with age and may disappear completely in older hyenas.^{2,3} The fur is soft and fluffy in young individuals and coarse in adults. The length from head to rump ranges between 95 and 150 cm, and the height at the withers ranges between 75 and 85 cm. Spotted hyenas have a 30–36 cm long tail covered with thick, black hair. In this sexually dimorphic species, females are about 6,6 kg heavier than males. Spotted hyenas have a large head and a massive, powerful neck. Their noses are black and smooth. The front legs are longer and stronger than the hind legs, giving

their backs a sloping appearance. Their feet have four toes with short, non-retractable, wide claws.^{4,5}

3. REPRODUCTION IN SPOTTED HYENAS (*CROCUTA CROCUTA*)

Spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) mate polygamously. Females are more dominant than males. This behavior ensures that the male withdraws if the female shows any aggression. Spotted hyenas do not have seasonal sexual cycles, and mating can occur throughout the year.⁶ Spotted hyenas, which exhibit polyestrous sexual activity, have an estrus period that lasts for two weeks. The gestation period is about 4 months (an average of 110 days). The vast majority of pregnancies result in twins, and twin births are common. However, the birth of 1 to 4 cubs can occur. Females give birth through their penis-like clitorises. During birth, the clitoris is torn to allow the passage of the cubs. The resulting wound takes a few weeks to heal. Figure 1 shows the appearance of the external genitalia of an adult spotted hyena during and after birth.^{7,8}

The cubs are not weaned until they are 14 to 18 months old. The cubs are born weighing 1 to 1,6 kg, with very early development of the eyes and ear canals. It has also been reported that the cubs have canines and incisors at birth. If the siblings are of the same sex, a violent fight begins and usually ends with the death of one of them. This is probably an adaptive instinct. When the cubs reach the age of 2 to 3 months, their black fur disappears, and they begin to develop the light-colored, spotted fur typical of adults. The cubs begin to exhibit hunting behavior at eight months old and join group hunts by the end of their first year. They reach puberty at approximately three years of age. The average lifespan in captivity is known to be between 12 and 25 years.³

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4. UROGENITAL CANAL IN FEMALE SPOTTED HYENAS (*CROCUTA CROCUTA*)

There are four different species of hyenas in the *Hyaenidae* family. These are spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*), striped hyenas (*Hyaena hyaena*), brown hyenas (*Parahyaena brunnea*), and aardwolves (*Proteles cristatus*). However, only spotted hyenas have a urogenital canal with a masculine appearance.⁹ Female spotted hyenas have a highly masculine appearance. The female genitals are very similar to those of males. The clitoris is enlarged, capable of erection, and resembles a penis. In addition, female spotted hyenas have a pair of scrotum-like sacs in the perineal region. However, these sacs are covered with more hair than those of males and do not contain testicles. The external vagina found in other mammal species is not present in female spotted hyenas. Instead, there is a urogenital canal called pseudopenis. The pseudopenis contains the urogenital canal that female spotted hyenas use for urination and mating. During birth, the cub or cubs also pass through this canal to exit the mother. Information on how this structure develops in female spotted hyenas varies.¹⁰

4.1. Structure of the Urogenital Canal

In female spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*), the genital canal consists of the ovaries, oviducts, and two pairs of cornua, which connect proximally to the uterus. The cervix is anatomically uncertain but has a unique histological structure. Located within the abdominal-pelvic cavity, the cervix connects caudally to the vagina. Just behind the vaginal segment, the urethra joins the genital canal to form the urogenital sinus (UGS). The UGS passes through the pelvic outlet, turns almost 180 degrees, and forms a penis-like structure. This structure is approximately the size of a flaccid penis and contains the clitoris. The urogenital canal of female spotted hyenas is on average 17 cm in length. The UGS extends from the proximal clitoris to the vagina, connecting with the urethra. A representative drawing of a section of the urogenital tract in a pregnant Spotted Hyena is presented in Figure 2.^{4,11}

In female spotted hyenas, there is a false structure called a pseudoscrotum, but no vaginal opening. There are no testicles in this scrotum-like structure. The appearance of the external genitalia in adult female and male spotted hyenas is shown in Figure 3.¹²

Figure 1: View of the external genital tract in the female spotted hyena during and after childbirth. A: The moment of birth of an adult spotted Hyena, B: External genital canal after birth in spotted hyenas, Arrow sign: indicates a tear that was torn and healed during childbirth.^{7,8}

Figure 2: A section of the urogenital canal in the pregnant spotted hyena. The urethra merges with the caudal of the vagina to form the urogenital sinus. This formation extends from the pelvic outlet and exhibits a penis-like appearance. UGS: Urogenital sinus.¹¹

4.2. Anatomy of the Urogenital Canal

In spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*), the female genital organs begin cranially with dense fatty tissue that includes the ovary and oviduct. The cornua uteri unite with the oviduct within this large fatty tissue and forms the corpus uteri caudally. The corpus uteri, starting from the bifurcation point, extends to the cervix, vagina, and urethra. The two corpora cavernosa, located almost in the middle of the urogenital canal, connect laterally to the pubic rami. The muscular ischiocavernosus, located at the junction of the pubic rami, covers the corpus. The bulbourethral gland is located in the pelvic cavity just cranial to the point where the pubic rami connect. The urogenital canal makes a 180-degree turn in the middle so that the proximal part of the clitoris faces ventrally and cranially. The bladder extends ventrally to the urethra, corpus uteri, cervix, and vagina. The urethra forms the urogenital sinus and extends caudally. The genital canal structure of a female spotted hyena is presented in Figure 4.⁹

5. FACTORS AFFECTING GENITAL TRACT DEVELOPMENT IN FEMALE SPOTTED HYENAS (*CROCUTA CROCUTA*)

The understanding of sexual differentiation in mammals is based on studies conducted by Alfred Jost in the 1940s. Jost's studies between 1947 and 1953 proved

the existence of hormones secreted by the fetal gonads. Research in this field also determined that the male urogenital phenotype develops with androgens secreted by the fetal testes.¹³ The presence of Anti-Müllerian hormone produced in the testes during the fetal period results in the regression of the Müllerian duct system, and thus sexual differentiation occurs.¹⁴ In line with this information, the formation and development of the urogenital system (UGS) have been associated with testicular androgens and Anti-Müllerian hormone. In addition, gender differences shaped in the brain and behavior have been accepted as the cause of the formation of male genital organs in mammals.¹⁵

5.1. Hormonal Influences on Genital System Differentiation

Matthews⁴ Matthews, in a study on the urogenital morphology of spotted hyenas, suggested that the fetal ovaries of hyenas may have produced androgens responsible for male genitalia. He supported this hypothesis with the abundance of interstitial tissue in the ovaries and the relative paucity of follicles. In another study, it was reported that the fetal ovaries of spotted hyenas produced testosterone, and it was thought that the changes in the urogenital canal structure were due to androgens produced during the fetal period.¹⁶ However, Licht et al.,¹⁷ in their studies on female spotted hyena

Figure 3: Appearance of external genitalia in adult female and male Spotted hyenas. A: Schematic drawing of the clitoris, pseudo-scrotum and anus in female Spotted hyenas. B: Appearance of genitalia in adult female Spotted hyenas. C: Appearance of genitalia in adult male Spotted hyenas.¹²

Figure 4: Reproductive tract anatomy in female spotted hyenas.⁹

fetuses, clearly determined that the androgen source supporting the formation of the penile clitoris is not the fetal ovary, but rather that this situation is shaped by different mechanisms. Other studies examining different stages of fetal development in spotted hyenas have shown that steroid hormones secreted during the fetal period play complex roles in the development of external genitalia, but that the formation of the penile clitoris is largely independent of androgens.^{11,16,18,19}

In various studies, it has been determined that the androgen found in circulation during postnatal life is largely androstenedione from the ovary, and that the androstenedione produced is converted to testosterone by the placenta and transferred to the fetuses. With this hypothesis, it has been proposed that hormones transferred via the umbilical route are effective in the differentiation of the external genital canal. It is known that such a transfer begins in the early stages of pregnancy and continues until birth. Therefore, it has been suggested that androgens present in the maternal circulation are a potential source for the developing female fetus. It has been proposed that male-like external genital morphology can be explained in this way.^{7,17,20} In another study investigating the effects of androgens, anti-androgen (flutamide and casodex) treatment was applied to spotted hyenas with confirmed pregnancies for 110 days, and the results of the treatment were monitored. Although maternal plasma testosterone and dihydrotestosterone concentrations were significantly reduced as a result of the treatment, it was determined that the penile clitoris preserved its presence in the females born.²¹

In recent years, it has been suggested that the morphological changes in the external genital system of female spotted hyenas may be related to estrogen, and a new hypothesis has been put forward. For this purpose, an aromatase enzyme inhibitor (Letrozole) was applied to pregnant spotted hyenas during periods when it would not negatively affect fetal development, and its effects on the penile clitoris and pseudoscrotum were investigated. The studies conducted determined that estrogen plays a critical role in the development of structures such as the urethra, penile clitoris, and pseudoscrotum. However, it was reported that the findings obtained in this study should be supported by further research.¹⁹

6. CONCLUSION

Female spotted hyenas, which are subspecies of the *Hyaenidae* family, which constitutes one of the smallest families of the predatory carnivores class, are distinguished from other hyena species by their genital structure. Female spotted hyenas have a masculine penile clitoris that is striking with its morphological and anatomical differences. This unique structure has made spotted hyenas the subject of various studies. Different hypotheses have been proposed based on these studies. Previous research on different species supports the fetal period sex differentiation model. Studies have shown that the formation of the genital tubercle in male and female spotted hyena fetuses occurs before fetal androgens begin to be secreted. Therefore, it is not possible to explain the masculine genital structures in female spotted hyenas using Jost's embryonal period sex differentiation model. Additionally, studies have shown that the effects

of anti-androgens applied during pregnancy on the penis and clitoris are minimal. The findings from all these studies indicate that androgens do not play a fundamental role in gonad development, contrary to previous beliefs. Finally, although recent studies have suggested that estrogen or estrogen/androgen interactions play an important role in the development of external genitalia, more detailed studies are needed to confirm this. It is recommended that future research focus specifically on beta estrogen receptor (ER β) signaling. This would allow for a more detailed investigation of the complex effects of estrogens on the development of external genitalia.

Authors contribution

BB: Research, planning, article review, writing- original draft and review.

Conflict of interest

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Data availability

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